

MODELLING OF THE THERMOFORMING PROCESS OF GLASS MAT REINFORCED
THERMOPLASTIC COMPOSITES.

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ABSTRACT

Glass mats combined with thermoplastic matrices make composites which are very interesting from the processing point of view but which also feature outstanding mechanical properties.

To predict the formability and the final shape as well as the material properties of GMTs, a model based on a microscopic level deformation mechanism is proposed. Matrix flow around the fibre is decomposed in two components: parallel with and perpendicular to the fibre. The local strain rate is expressed as a function of these two components. Minimisation of internal energy dissipation allows to find the contribution of each component.

From a given orientation distribution function (ODF) of the fibre in a flat panel it is then possible, with the knowledge of the local strain, to predict the new ODF in the thermoformed part. The prediction of the ODF can then further be used to predict the formability and the final shape by means of the calculation of yield loci.

KEYWORDS: Composites; fibre orientation/ODF; thermoforming; modelisation/yield locus.

1. INTRODUCTION

One of the most attractive processing techniques for converting thermoplastic composites into parts is thermoforming. Cold sheet forming is a widely used low cost and fast rate process in the sheet metal forming industry. If composites processing can be done in existing metal forming equipment with minimal modifications, these composites will find acceptance more easily as replacements for sheet metal. However, present information on the behavior of these

composites during molding and mechanical characteristics in the molded part is still fragmentary. Most of the time, formability is experimentally evaluated for a specific material¹⁻⁴. Kinematic models are also often presented when studying forming of complex 3-dimensional parts from woven, knitted or UD composite plates⁵⁻⁷. In this report, we present a model for deformation of short fibres mats based on energetics considerations. The final purpose of this model is to be used in an elasto-plastic FEM software. Finite element methods can be used to solve the problem only when the constitutive equations are known. We shall thus focus our attention on the modelling of the evolution of the microstructure geometry as a function of the deformation history, based on the minimisation of the dissipated plastic power. Closely related to the description of the microstructure, a model which predicts the amount of energy associated with each mode of deformation is also developed. Microstructure and energetics may then be combined to provide the constitutive relations for the composite. The material considered is a thermoplastic sheet reinforced with a chopped strand mat. During processing, the sheet is heated just above its T_g so that large deformation can occur.

2. MICROSTRUCTURE

The fibres of the initial part are distributed in the matrix in a random order. However, as the part deforms, the fibre orientation will not remain random and thus the properties of the material will change. Hence, a method to describe the orientation of the fibre at each instant in time must be developed. Since there are usually millions of fibres in each small volume, it would be impossible to define the position of each individual fibre and then track each fibre's position as the part deforms. Instead, a statistically accurate description of the distribution of fibre orientations must be developed. This description may be called the "Orientation Distribution Function" or "ODF", a term which is borrowed from those investigating textures of metals.

2.1. Theoretical basis:

Let a material (here a plate) have a reference system $\{X\}$ and a fibre, which lies in the material, have a reference system $\{X^f\}$. In its reference system, the x_3^f axis direction coincides with the fibre (fig. 1).

fig. 1

The coordinate transformation of one reference system to the other one (e.g. $\{X\}$ to $\{X^f\}$) can be done by three successive rotations:

- 1° rotation of angle φ_1 around axis x_3 ,
- 2° rotation of angle Φ around the new axis x_1 ,
- 3° rotation of angle φ_2 around the new axis x_3 .

The three angles φ_1 , Φ , φ_2 are called the Euler angles. Each of those rotations can be described by a matrix ($[R_{\varphi_1}], [R_{\Phi}], [R_{\varphi_2}]$) and the multiplication of those three matrixes gives the transformation matrix ($[R_{\varphi_2}] \cdot [R_{\Phi}] \cdot [R_{\varphi_1}] = [T]$) of one reference system to the other one. All the possible transformations can be described with:

$$0 \leq \varphi_1 \leq 2\pi, \quad 0 \leq \Phi \leq \pi, \quad 0 \leq \varphi_2 \leq 2\pi$$

2.2. ODF formulation:

The fibre orientation can thus be described by means of the three Euler angles which transform the fibre reference system into the material reference system. We will take the material reference system with x_2 as the longitudinal direction, x_1 as the transverse direction and x_3 as the perpendicular direction (fig. 2).

fig. 2

For a tridimensional ODF, the three Euler angles must be considered, while for the case of bidimensional ODF, only one angle changes, the other ones are fixed. For the following, we will use a bidimensional ODF with φ_1 as variable, Φ equal to 90° (because the fibre is defined following the x_3^f direction) and φ_2 equal to 0° . In other words, the ODF can be defined only by φ_1 , the angle between the fibre and the longitudinal direction of the pate. It is then possible to represent the ODF by means of histograms like in figure 3. Each peak of this histogram represents the fibre concentration v_{fi} which lies in each angle interval i . The accuracy of this representation and thus the accuracy of the calculation that uses the ODF is thus directly a function of the angle discretisation. In order to see how the ODF changes during a deformation process, it is better to use a continuous ODF. That can be done by

representing each peak of the histogram by a Gaussian function; the summation on those Gaussians gives the ODF (fig. 4).

fig. 3: ODF represented by means of histogram

fig. 4: Continuous representation of the ODF

3. ENERGETICS

3.1. Evolution of the microstructure:

Let a deformation mode for a small volume of the composite plate described in the reference system $\{X\}$ in terms of displacement rate gradient tensor be:

$$\dot{K}_{ij} = \frac{\delta v_i}{\delta x_j} \quad (1)$$

where v is the displacement rate and x a coordinate point..

In the reference system $\{X^f\}$ we will then have:

$$\dot{K}_{ij}^f = \frac{\delta v_i^f}{\delta x_j^f} \quad (2)$$

For this deformation mode $\dot{\mathbf{K}}$, we should normally find the matrix deformation $\dot{\mathbf{M}}(\mathbf{x})$ and the fibre deformation $\dot{\mathbf{F}}(\mathbf{x})$ function of the position \mathbf{x} in the considered composite volume. This could be achieved by using the FE-method, but the problem here would be that the meshing will be too fine and that the calculation time will then be quite great. Therefore we will assume that the matrix has the same (homogeneous) deformation as that of the composite. That means that in each part of the matrix, the matrix deformation $\dot{\mathbf{M}}$ is constant and equal to the given deformation $\dot{\mathbf{K}}$.

We will also assume that:

-the fibres are and remain straight.

-the fibre doesn't deform. Longitudinal and transversal strain of the fibre are so small with regard to that of the matrix, that we can neglect them. So $\dot{F}_{ii}^f = 0$ ($i = 1$ to 3)

-the diameter of the fibre is so small that we can neglect it: that means that direction x_1^f and x_2^f must not be considered for the fibre displacement rate gradient tensor. So $\dot{F}_{12}^f, \dot{F}_{21}^f, \dot{F}_{31}^f, \dot{F}_{32}^f$ may be supposed equal to zero.

Under such hypothesis we can express the velocity fields as follows:

$$\text{for the matrix: } v_i^{mf} = v_i^{mo} + \dot{K}_{ij}^f \cdot x_j^f \quad (i, j = 1 \text{ à } 3) \quad (3),$$

$$\text{for the fibre: } v_i^{ff} = v_i^{fo} + \dot{F}_{i3}^f \cdot x_3^f \quad (i = 1, 2) \quad (4)$$

where v_i^{mf} and v_i^{ff} are respectively the displacement rate of the matrix and of the fibre in the fibre reference system, v_i^{mo} and v_i^{fo} are the relative displacement rate with respect to a fixed origin O. These are introduced to allow also the description of long fibres with our model in the future.

The aim is now to calculate the value of the \dot{F}_{i3}^f coefficients because they give the rotation of the fibre. That can be done by minimisation of the dissipated power at the interface matrix-fibre as a function of those coefficients.

3.1.1. Calculation of the dissipated power at the matrix-fibre interface:

Due to the symmetry of fibre, we will consider that the matrix flow around the fibre may be decomposed in a flow transversal and parallel to the fibre.

Therefore we can also decompose the dissipated power (rate of energy dissipation) at the matrix-fibre interface P_f into two parts: one which represents the dissipated power transverse to the fibre P_t , the other parallel to the fibre P_l . In order to calculate those two components of the dissipated power, we will introduce two 'friction' parameters μ_l and μ_t which represent the longitudinal and the transverse friction at the interface matrix-fibre. A discussion of μ_l and μ_t is presented in section 3.2.1. . We can now write for a fibre i (that means with Euler angle $\varphi_1^i, \Phi^i, \varphi_2^i$ in the ODF histogram):

$$P_{ii} = \mu_t \cdot 2 \cdot \int_0^{l/2} \sqrt{[(v_1^{mfi} - v_1^{ffi})^2 + (v_2^{mfi} - v_2^{ffi})^2]} dx^{fi_3} \quad (5)$$

$$P_{li} = \mu_1 \cdot 2 \cdot \int_0^{l/2} \sqrt{[(v_3^{mfi} - v_3^{ffi})^2]} dx^{fi_3} \quad (6)$$

where l is the fibre length.

Minimisation of this dissipated power:

$$\frac{\delta(P_t+P_l)}{\delta \dot{F}_{13}^f} = \frac{\delta P_f}{\delta \dot{F}_{13}^f} = 0 \quad (7)$$

$$\text{results in: } \dot{F}_{13}^f = \dot{K}_{13}^f \quad (8a)$$

$$\dot{F}_{23}^f = \dot{K}_{23}^f \quad (8b)$$

(The other coefficients \dot{F}_{ij}^f are equal to zero because of our hypothesis).

3.1.2. Discussion:

For the case of short fibres, v_1^{mo} and v_1^{fo} are equal when there is no interaction between the fibres. Indeed, a short fibre without any interaction then these one of the matrix will necessary flow as the matrix

Only \dot{F}_{13}^f and \dot{F}_{23}^f are different from zero. That means that the displacement of the fibre is a rotation around x_1^f and x_2^f . By applying these rotations on the initial orientation of the fibre, we find the new fibre orientation. By such procedure on all the fibre i of the ODF, it is then possible to find the new ODF after a deformation increment.

The equivalence of \dot{F}_{13}^f and \dot{F}_{23}^f with \dot{K}_{13}^f and \dot{K}_{23}^f means that no relative transverse motion between the fibre and the matrix occurs. The fibre must follow the matrix displacement. By introducing (8a) and (8b) into (5), it can be shown that P_{ii} equals zero.

The dissipated power at the matrix-fibre interface P_f is equal to P_l and is then only a function of \dot{K}_{33}^f which represents the relative deformation between the fibre (which doesn't deform ($\dot{F}_{33}^f=0$)) and the matrix (which deforms as \dot{K}):

$$P_{li} = \mu_1 \cdot 2 \cdot \int_0^{l/2} [\dot{K}_{33}^{fi} \cdot x^{fi_3}] dx^{fi_3} \quad (9)$$

3.2. Calculation of the yield locus:

The yield locus can be calculated by means of the dissipated power. We know that

$$P = \sigma : \dot{\epsilon} = \sigma : \dot{K} = \sigma : E \cdot \dot{\epsilon}_{eq} \quad (10)$$

where σ is the (unknown) average stress, \mathbf{E} the deformation mode and $\dot{\epsilon}_{\text{eq}}$ the equivalent strain rate. For the next, we will take the definition of Von Mises for $\dot{\epsilon}_{\text{eq}}$:

$$\dot{\epsilon}_{\text{eq}} = \dot{\epsilon}_{\text{vm}} = \sqrt{2/3 \cdot \dot{\epsilon}_{ij} \cdot \dot{\epsilon}_{ij}} \quad (11)$$

If we want to evaluate the stress level (the yield stress) which gives plastic deformation for a given stress mode \mathbf{U} ($\sigma = \sigma_{\text{eq}} \mathbf{U}$), we must minimise the following expression:

$$\sigma_{\text{eq}} = \frac{P}{(\mathbf{U} : \mathbf{E} \cdot \dot{\epsilon}_{\text{vm}})} \quad (12)$$

Because this minimum must be found out of quite a large number of deformation modes \mathbf{E} , a strategy based on the material symmetry is used in order to decrease this number of deformation modes. We can then find that for an orthotropic material 9500 different deformation modes are needed⁸.

The yield locus can then be found by calculation of the yield stress for different stress modes. By representing this yield locus by an analytical expressions it is then possible to implement them into a FEM-software⁹.

3.2.1. Calculation of the total dissipated power:

Until now, we have only used the dissipated power at the matrix-fibre interface in order to calculate the new ODF. The total power dissipated in the composite is the sum of the dissipated power at the matrix-fibre interface and the dissipated power in the matrix:

$$P_c = P_m^c + P_f^c \quad (13)$$

3.2.1.1. Dissipated power at the matrix-fibre interface:

We have seen that for a fibre i the dissipated power is:

$$P_{\text{fi}} = P_{\text{li}} + P_{\text{ti}} \quad (14)$$

In order to calculate P_{li} and P_{ti} we have defined in section 3.1.1. two 'friction' parameters, μ_l and μ_t . They represent the force by unit length of the fibre that we have to apply to the fibre in order to get a relative displacement between the matrix and the fibre. Because for the case of short fibres there is no relative transversal flow between the matrix and the fibre ($P_{\text{ti}} = 0$), we will not develop at this stage the physical meaning of μ_t . On the other hand, the relative flow parallel to the fibre is equal to \dot{K}_{33}^{fi} ($\dot{K}_{33}^{\text{fi}} - \dot{F}_{33}^{\text{fi}}$ and $\dot{F}_{33}^{\text{fi}} = 0$) and μ_l can be represented by the critical shear stress of the interface $\tau_c^{\text{interface}}$ multiplied with the circumference of the fibre:

$$\mu_l = \tau_c^{\text{interface}} \cdot \pi \cdot d \quad (15)$$

If the interface is very strong (that is the case for example for a glass-PET composite), the shear strain will not occur at the interface but further away in the matrix. That means that we can take the critical shear stress as the one of the matrix:

$$\tau_c^{\text{interface}} = \tau_c^{\text{matrix}} \quad (16)$$

In our hypothesis (section 3.1.) we assumed that the matrix deformation is homogeneous and equal to the external applied deformation. In reality, as described here, an additional shear strain occurs in the matrix around each fibre. That means that for a single-fibre system, we have to use an effective fibre diameter d' in order to take into account that the effective matrix deformation doesn't occur at the interface but well in the matrix.

$$d' = \alpha \cdot d \quad (\text{with } \alpha > 1) \quad (17)$$

α increases with the matrix viscosity but is also function of the interface quality. It can be evaluated by experimental tests.

If the fibres are too close to each other (high fibre concentration), this will result in a complex matrix deformation. This decreases the validity of the above mentioned hypothesis and so, the actual model to predict the ODF is more appropriate for a small fibre concentration than for a higher fibre concentration.

Because the critical shear stress is also a function of the matrix deformation, we have to introduce an experimental parameter for the determination of the effective critical shear stress:

$$\tau_c = \beta \cdot \tau_c^{\text{matrix}} \quad (18)$$

β is function of the ODF and of the fibre concentration.

Then, by solving equation 9, we see that for one fibre i:

$$P_{fi} = \mu_1 \cdot 2 \cdot \int_0^{1/2} |K_{33}^{fi}| \cdot x_3^{fi} \cdot dx_3^{fi} = \dot{\epsilon}_{vm} \cdot \tau_c \cdot \pi \cdot d' \cdot l^2 \cdot |E_{33}^{fi}| / 4 \quad (19)$$

Then, for all the fibres:

$$P_f^f = \dot{\epsilon}_{vm} \cdot \sum P_{fi} \cdot v_{fi} = \dot{\epsilon}_{vm} \cdot \tau_c \cdot \pi \cdot d' \cdot l^2 / 4 \cdot \sum_i |E_{33}^{fi}| \cdot v_{fi} \quad (20)$$

To get the dissipated power in a unit volume, P_f^f must be multiplied by the number of fibres per unit volume of composite. That is

$$P_f^c = \dot{\epsilon}_{vm} \cdot \sum P_{fi} \cdot v_{fi} \cdot V_f / (\pi \cdot d'^2 \cdot l / 4) = \dot{\epsilon}_{vm} \cdot \tau_c \cdot l \cdot V_f / d' \cdot \sum_i |E_{33}^{fi}| \cdot v_{fi} \quad (21)$$

3.2.1.2. Dissipated power in the matrix:

The matrix is considered as an incompressible rigid-plastic material which obeys to the Von Mises yield criterion:

$$\sigma_{vm}^m = \sigma_0 \quad (22)$$

where σ_0 is the yield stress in a uniaxial tensile test of the matrix without fibres and σ_{vm}^m is the Von Mises equivalent strain defined as:

$$\sigma_{vm}^m = \sqrt{[(\sigma_x - \sigma_y)^2 / 2 + (\sigma_y - \sigma_z)^2 / 2 + (\sigma_z - \sigma_x)^2 / 2 + 3(\tau_{yz}^2 + \tau_{zx}^2 + \tau_{xy}^2)]} \quad (23)$$

For pure shear:

$$\sqrt{3} \cdot \tau_c = \sigma_{vm}^m \quad (24)$$

As dissipated power in the matrix equals :

$$P_m^m = \sigma_{vm}^m \cdot \dot{\epsilon}_{vm} \quad (25)$$

then

$$P_m^m = \tau_c \cdot \sqrt{3} \cdot \dot{\epsilon}_{vm} \quad (26)$$

P_m^m is the dissipated power per unit volume of matrix. Per unit volume composite we have:

$$P_m^c = (1-V_f) \cdot P_m^m \quad (27)$$

3.2.1.3. Dissipated power in the composite:

For the whole composite material, the dissipated power is :

$$P_c = P_m^c + P_f^c = \tau_c \cdot \dot{\epsilon}_{vm} \cdot [(1-V_f) \cdot \sqrt{3} + (V_f \cdot l/d) \sum_i |E_{33}^{fi}| \cdot v_{fi}] \quad (28)$$

We can also write:

$$P_c = \tau_c \cdot \dot{\epsilon}_{vm} \cdot C_m \left(\frac{\dot{\epsilon}_{ij}}{\dot{\epsilon}_{vm}} \right) \quad (29)$$

$$\text{where } C_m \left(\frac{\dot{\epsilon}_{ij}}{\dot{\epsilon}_{vm}} \right) = [(1-V_f) \cdot \sqrt{3} + (V_f \cdot l/d) \sum_i |E_{33}^{fi}| \cdot v_{fi}] \quad (30)$$

We will call C_m the power factor.

3.2.2. Discussion:

If we compare relation 29 with the following one:

$$P = \sigma_{eq} \cdot \dot{\epsilon}_{vm} \quad (31)$$

we can see that the equivalent stress σ_{eq} is proportional to τ_c and C_m . The power factor C_m is only a function of the material geometry (the ODF) and of the deformation mode. τ_c is only a function of the process parameters (temperature, deformation rate, pressure,...). That is important because the minimisation of equation 12 for the calculation of the yield locus is time consuming. So, instead of equation 12, it is better to minimize:

$$\frac{\sigma}{\tau_c} = \frac{P}{U : E \cdot \dot{\epsilon}_{vm}} \quad (32)$$

in order to calculate the yield locus. This means that each time a process parameter will change, we don't have to recalculate the whole yield locus, but just to reactualize τ_c . The yield locus must be reactualized only when the ODF of the material changes.

4. EXAMPLE

The first example will be the case of an aligned discontinuous fibre thermoplastic composite sheet. For such a material the ODF histogram is presented by one single peak. So, if a tensile strain is applied in the direction of the fiber, the summation in expression 28 may be replaced by 1. By doing so, we obtain the same yield stress expression as the one obtained by Okine et al.¹⁰. Their experimental verification confirms the validity of this calculation.

As a second example, we show here the calculated evolution of the ODF (fig. 5) as well as the yield locus (fig. 6) of an initial isotropic material for an imposed deformation mode given by:

$$\dot{\mathbf{K}} = \begin{bmatrix} \dot{\epsilon}_{11} & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & -\dot{\epsilon}_{11}/2 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & -\dot{\epsilon}_{11}/2 \end{bmatrix}$$

This tensor describes approximatively a tensile test with a Poisson coefficient equal to 0,5.

fig. 5: Evolution of the ODF in function of the deformation

fig. 6: Evolution of the yield locus during the deformation (same legend as fig. 5)

In figure 6, it is in fact the intersection with the 1-2 plane of the material reference system which is represented, because the whole yield locus is six-dimensional and cannot simply be represented.

The knowledge of the ODF gives also the possibility to calculate the elastical properties of the deformed part, by using for example the laminate analogy, to predict the mechanical properties for randomly oriented composites¹¹.

5. CONCLUSION

In order to be able to simulate, by means of FEM, the deformation behavior of thermoplastic plates reinforced with short fibres when submitted to a thermoforming process, we have described here a model which predicts the evolution of the fibre orientation. That allows us to calculate the evolution of the yield locus at each time of the deformation process and also to predict the elastic properties of the deformed part. The model will be further developed for the case of continuous random fibre.

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